

OXIDATIVE STABILITY OF RED PALM OIL FROM TWO OIL PALM VARIETIES – *Elaeis guineensis* and *Elaeis oleifera*: COMPARATIVE EFFECTS OF STORAGE TEMPERATURE AND DURATION

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ABSTRACT

The oxidative stability of red palm oil (RPO) from two oil palm varieties subjected to different storage temperatures and durations was studied. RPO was prepared from mature and ripe fruits of *E. guineensis* (EG) and *E. oleifera* (EO). Samples of the oils were stored at 4°C and 25°C and analyzed immediately after extraction, at 6 weeks, and at 12 weeks. The moisture and free fatty acid contents, peroxide and anisidine values of the oils were determined using standard analytical protocols. The results show that the moisture content of EO did not vary significantly ($p > 0.05$) with either duration or temperature of storage. It was however significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than the values obtained for EG at all points. The free fatty acid contents for EG were statistically similar ($p > 0.05$) for both storage temperatures at the 6th and 12th weeks (range 13.4% to 13.8%). At all storage points, EO had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher values compared to EG. The peroxide value (Meq hydroperoxide/kg oil) of EO increased markedly at 6 weeks of storage from 5.0 ± 0.1 to 8.6 ± 0.2 . The oil from EG had significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower peroxide values at all storage temperatures and durations compared to the oil from EO. The anisidine values of the oils rose from 0 at the beginning of the study to 1.22 ± 0.02 at 6 weeks (EO; 4°C). The oil from EG had better oxidative stability indices than that from EO and 4°C, appears to be a better storage temperature, especially for EG.

KEYWORDS: *Elaeis guineensis*, *Elaeis oleifera*, oxidative stability, red palm oil

INTRODUCTION

Red palm oil comes from the fruit of the oil palm tree generally grown in West and Central Africa, Malaysia and Indonesia. The oil is isolated by various methods including boiling the seeds, maceration and pressing (Bangash *et al.*, 2004). The main fatty acids in red palm oil are palmitic and oleic acids; and it is a good source of β -carotene (Henry, 2011).

Palm oil accounts for 30% of the global vegetable oils production and is one of the 17 major oils and fats produced and traded worldwide (Carter *et al.*, 2007). It is therefore a very important commodity especially in the food industry. Palm oil quality and stability are main factors that influence its acceptability and market value. One of the most important indicators of the keeping quality of oil is its oxidative stability (Tan and Che Man, 2002). The mechanisms by which lipids alter in the presence of oxygen are generally referred to as rancidity – a factor that is becoming increasingly important as manufacturers require longer shelf-lives and because the public are becoming more aware of nutritional issues (Gan *et al.*, 2005). The development of pungent and offensive off-flavour, destruction of vitamins, fatty acids, carotenes and chlorophylls, amino acids, etc are all known effects of the oxidative deterioration of oils. This oxidation promotes the formation of new compounds such as diacyl-glycerols, monoglycerols, free fatty acids and other oxidative substances that are harmful to humans (Clark and Serbia, 1991; Tarmizi and Lin, 2008).

In Nigeria, palm oil production is a commercial enterprise especially among rural dwellers in the Southern parts of the country. Because of seasonal variation in the availability of oil palm fruits, and therefore availability and supply of palm oil, bulk storage of the product is often a common practice (Henry, 2011). This practice in turn makes red palm oil susceptible to oxidative and hydrolytic deterioration, and then the attendant negative consequences on health and economics. This study therefore investigated the oxidative stability of red palm oil from two varieties of the oil palm, stored at refrigeration and room temperatures, and for different durations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of *Elaeis guineensis* and *Elaeis oleifera* fruits

Mature and ripe fruits of *E. guineensis* and *E. oleifera* were harvested from the National Institute for Oil palm Research (NIFOR) palm plantation, Benin, Nigeria. Two bunches of each species were harvested, pilled-up and covered with plantain leaves for three days. Thereafter, the loosened fruits were removed from the central core and spike-lets. They were then sorted to remove bad fruits and the good fruits cleaned and used for the extraction of oil.

Extraction of red palm oil

The clean fruits (for each species) were boiled in tap water for two hours, and thereafter pulverized into a mash. The mash was then fed into a screw press where the oil was extracted. The extracted oil was clarified by boiling for thirty minutes. Thereafter the oil was allowed to cool and decanted into properly labeled containers and stored on the shelf or in a refrigerator until used for the analyses. The sludge-like sediment was properly disposed.

Chemical analyses

Free fatty acids (FFA), peroxide value (PV), and *p*-Anisidine value (AV) determinations were carried using AOCS official methods Ca 5a-40, Cd 8-53 and Cd 18-90 (AOCS, 1996). Moisture content was determined using the MPOB Test Method p2.1; Part 1 (MPOB, 2004). The analyses were carried out immediately after extraction, at six weeks and at twelve weeks of storage.

Statistical analyses

Data collected were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis. Thereafter the differences between means were separated by one way ANOVA with a significant threshold fixed at 0.05. The data analyses were done using SPSS for windows version 11.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL). The results are presented as means \pm standard deviations, in line graphs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The moisture content of *E. oleifera* did not vary significantly ($p > 0.05$) with either duration of storage or storage temperature. It was however significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than the values obtained for *E. guineensis* at all points. The moisture contents of *E. guineensis* increased marginally with storage (irrespective of storage temperature) from 2.6% to 2.9% (Fig.1). Because the oxidative stability of palm oil in storage is affected by moisture content (Bangash *et al.*, 2004), the higher moisture content of *E. guineensis* apparently predisposes it to a higher risk of oxidative deterioration.

Figure 2 shows the free fatty acid contents of the palm oils. There were significant ($p < 0.05$) variations between the free fatty acid contents of *E. oleifera* stored at 4°C and 25°C at the 6th and 12th weeks of storage respectively. The values for *E. guineensis* were statistically similar ($p > 0.05$) for both storage temperatures (at both the 6th and 12th weeks), but increased marginally from 13.4% to 13.8% (25°C) and 14.2% (4°C). At all storage points, *E. oleifera* had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher values compared to *E. guineensis*. Free fatty acids are produced by the hydrolytic action of the enzyme lipase or by the oxidation of triacylglycerols in oils, in the presence of water and oxygen (oxidizing environment), during the course of storage (Bensmira *et al.*, 2007). Oxidation leads to rancidity and toxicity and is the single most important reaction of vegetable oils (Gan *et al.*, 2005). The determination of free fatty acids by titration is known not to differentiate between acids formed by oxidation and those formed by hydrolysis (Sherwin, 1968). It is usually measured as an index of hydrolytic rancidity and is important in the food industry since free acids contribute to the development of off-flavours and off-odours in the oil (Gan *et al.*, 2005). It appears that there was more hydrolytic activity in the *E. oleifera* samples irrespective of storage conditions than in the *E. guineensis* samples. This may not also be unconnected with the higher water activity in the *E. oleifera* samples.

The peroxide value of *E. oleifera* increased markedly at 6 weeks of storage, with the value of the oil stored at 25°C being significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than that of the same oil stored at 4°C. The difference in the mean peroxide values for the oil were not significantly ($p > 0.05$) different between the 6th week and the 12th week (within the same storage temperature). The peroxide values of *E. guineensis* followed a similar (albeit less ascending) pattern as that of *E. oleifera*. However, samples of the oil from *E. guineensis* has significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower peroxide values at all storage temperatures and throughout the duration of storage compared to the oil from *E. oleifera* (Fig. 3). The extent of oil deterioration is best reflected in the changes in peroxide value

and free fatty acid content. The peroxide value is one of the most widely used tests for oxidative rancidity. It is a measure of the concentration of peroxides and hydroperoxides formed in the initial stages of lipid oxidation (Bangash *et al.*, 2004). Peroxides are however unstable and can break down to carbonyl and aldehydic compounds under conditions of high heat, air, and light (Perkins, 1967). Increase in peroxide values of the oils with increase in storage temperature therefore indicates an increase in oxidative rancidity of the oils. The data clearly shows that *E. oleifera* had more oxidative rancidity relative to *E. guineensis* and this may be related again to its higher moisture content. However, it appears (given the data) that with respect to temperature variation and storage duration, rancidity increased more due to oxidation than to lipase activity.

Figure 4 shows that the anisidine values of the oils rose from zero at the beginning of the study to 1.22 at 6 weeks (*E. oleifera*; 4°C). The values were significantly ($p > 0.05$) lower for the same oil stored at 25°C at both week 6 and week 12. Conversely, the oil from *E. guineensis* stored at 4°C had higher anisidine values than that of the same oil stored at 25°C. The sharp rise in the anisidine values of both oils from week 0 to week 6 was attenuated between week 6 and week 12. The anisidine value of oils is a measure of secondary oxidation products such as aldehydes and ketones which are transformed from the primary oxidation products. Anisidine values not exceeding 2 units are usually desirable (Tarmizi and Lin, 2008). The fact that the anisidine values of both oils remained lower than 2 units even at 12 weeks suggests that primary oxidation was the major contributor to rancidity in the studied oils at the said duration of storage.

In conclusion, the data from this study show that the oil from *E. guineensis* had better oxidative stability indices than that from *E. oleifera*. The oxidative stability of both oils deteriorated marginally with storage, while 4°C appeared to be a better storage temperature, especially for *E. guineensis*.

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Fig. 1: Moisture contents of the oils stored at different temperatures and for varying durations

Fig. 2: Free fatty acids in the oils stored at different temperatures and for varying durations

Fig. 3: Peroxide values of the oils stored at different temperatures and for varying durations

Fig. 4: Anisidine values of the oils stored at different temperatures and for varying durations

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